

PROBLEMS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS IN THE REGION AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM

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Abstract. *In our country, the growing focus on the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship has significantly improved their economic indicators, bringing them closer to global standards, thanks to the favorable conditions available for this sector.*

The creation of conducive conditions for free enterprise has resulted in the growth and expansion of small business enterprises in our country.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, emphasized the importance of developing small businesses and private entrepreneurship in his first address to the Oliy Majlis, stating: “As we have declared 2018 as the Year of Supporting Active Entrepreneurship, Innovative Ideas, and Technologies, next year, developing active entrepreneurship will be at the center of our attention. Necessary measures will be taken to support this sector and eliminate obstacles and barriers to the rapid and sustainable development of business entities.”

Keywords: *economic indicators, free enterprise, small business, private entrepreneurship, favorable conditions, development, active entrepreneurship, innovative ideas.*

INTRODUCTION

Systematic measures are being implemented in Uzbekistan to comprehensively and systematically support small businesses and regional entrepreneurship, ensure their sustainable development, increase their share in gross domestic product (GDP), production, and employment, meet the demand for credit resources, and create a favorable business environment.

This dissertation research contributes to the implementation of the tasks outlined in several key regulatory and legal documents, including the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," Decree No. PF-4848 dated October 5, 2016, "On Additional Measures to Ensure the Rapid Development of Entrepreneurial Activity, Comprehensive Protection of Private Property, and Improvement of the Business Environment," Decree No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017, "On the Action Strategy for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan," as well as Resolution No. PQ-4525 dated November 20, 2019, "On Measures to Further Improve the Business Environment and Enhance the System of Supporting Entrepreneurship," and other regulatory and legal documents related to this activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The theoretical aspects and methodological foundations of developing small business and private entrepreneurship activities have been covered in the scientific works of foreign scholars such as J.B. Say, A. Smith, A. Marshall, J. Schumpeter, J. Keynes, R. Hisrich, M. Peters, F. Hayek, M. Lapusta, Y. Starostin, K. McConnell, S. Brue, and others. [1]

In addition, researchers from the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) have conducted studies and econometric modeling on the field of small business and private entrepreneurship, including V.M. Vlasova, A. Raisky, A. Shestakov, N.Ye. Yegorova, V.M. Savchenko, V.M. Shepelov, M.A. Fedotova, and others. [1]

Despite the conducted scientific research and theoretical-methodological studies, the comprehensive statistical analysis of regional small business activities in the context of economic modernization, the evaluation and forecasting of factors affecting economic activity based on econometric models, have not been systematically addressed. The studies have been limited to exploring the characteristics of certain regions, without a thorough examination of Navoi region as a distinct research object. This gap led to the selection of the research topic and the definition of its goals and objectives.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The steady increase in the share of small businesses across all sectors of the economy prevents imbalances between various fields within the country and creates a foundation for the formation of an effective competitive environment in each sector.

The statistical analysis of the share, production volume, and dynamics of goods and services created by small businesses and private entrepreneurship entities in Uzbekistan across various sectors provides the opportunity to draw necessary conclusions about the state of the sector.

In developed countries, small businesses are rapidly growing. Governments pay significant attention to such enterprises, creating conditions to support them through various programs and incentives. In most developed countries, small businesses serve as a foundation for sustainable growth, providing employment opportunities for the majority of the population. In these countries, small enterprises contribute 50–70% of GDP.

In analyzing the economic condition of small businesses in Navoi region, the main database is provided by the economic indicators of small business activities available at the Statistics Agency and its regional divisions.

The share of small businesses and private entrepreneurship (SBPE) in various sectors and fields of the regional economy is presented in Table 2.5.

Table 1

The Share of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship in Navoi Region (in percentages) [2]

<i>Years</i>	<i>ЯХМ</i>	<i>Industry</i>	<i>Construction</i>	<i>Export</i>	<i>Import</i>
2015	51,0	19,4	75,8	14,9	15,1
2016	50,4	20,8	74,8	21,5	10,8
2017	49,4	19,4	75,4	20,0	18,3
2018	42,3	16,8	72,9	29,5	15,3
2019	31,0	8,4	71,9	26,2	65,1
2020	25,7	6,5	74,1	11,8	35,1
2021	27,1	6,6	75,6	11,6	26,0
2022	25,9	7,2	80,4	8,7	34,5
2023	26,0	7,7	79,1	9,0	36,2

As a result of the attention given to the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship, their share in the gross regional product (GRP) in Navoi region decreased from

51.0% in 2015 to 26.0% in 2023, representing a decline of 25.0%. The share of SBPE (Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship) in the industrial sector dropped from 19.4% in 2015 to 7.7% in 2023. In contrast, the share of SBPE in the construction sector increased to 79.1% in 2023, compared to 75.8% in 2015, reflecting a growth of 3.3%.

The share of SBPE in exports within the region was 14.9% in 2015, but this figure decreased to 9.0% by 2023. The insufficient share of SBPE in the industrial sector and exports highlights the need to revisit and revise the tasks implemented in these areas.

Over the past nine years, the share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the region’s GRP has decreased almost twofold (from 51% to 26%), while providing employment for 60% of the population. However, it should be noted that creating a favorable environment for the development of the sector requires taking into account the specific characteristics of each region. The share of SBPE in industrial production, per capita product, and employment in Navoi region can be grouped by cities and districts, as shown in Table 2.6.

Table 2

Statistical Grouping of SBPE Share by Districts in Navoi Region [3]

Grouping criteria	Grouping level	Composition of groups (region, district, city) and share (%)
Share in the region's industry (as of 01.01.2024)	The highest	Gozgon city, Uchkuduk, and Tomdi districts (100.0%)
	High	Zarafshan city (99.0%), Kiziltepa (98.5%), and Nurata (86.2%) districts
	Average	Khatirchi district (49.6%)
	Low	Karmana district (23.2%)
	Very low	Navoi city (1.7%)
Share of the region's population in employment (as of 01.01.2023)	High	Gozgon city (73.1%), Khatirchi (72.4%), and Nurata (71.7%) districts
	Average	Tomdi (68.6%), Kiziltepa (68.0%), Navbahor (67.8%), and Karmana (67.1%) districts
	Low	Konimekh (39.5%) and Uchkuduk (32.6%) districts, as well as Zarafshan (25.0%) and Navoi (21.5%) cities

When the cities and districts of Navoi region were statistically grouped by the share of SBPE (Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship) in industrial production, the districts of Navbahor, Nurata, and Tomdi, which do not host large industrial enterprises, were included in the highest group. In contrast, Karmana and Konimekh districts, as well as Navoi city, were placed in the lower groups due to their low indicators in this regard.

When statistically grouping the cities and districts of the region by the share of SBPE in employment, Navbahor and Khatirchi districts were classified in the highest group. Meanwhile,

Navoi and Zarafshan cities, as well as Uchkuduk district, were placed in the lower group for this indicator.

In these cases, the grouping criteria for cities and districts were based on the indicators of the Republic and Navoi region.

This situation is also observed in the changes in the share of small business and private entrepreneurship entities across sectors and fields (Table 2.7).

Table 3

Share of Small Business Entities by Sectors in 2023, % [4]

Sector, field name	Ўзбекистон Республикаси	Navoi region	Navoi city	Zarafshan city	Gozgon city	Karmana district	Konimekh district	Kiziltepa district	Navbahor district	Nurata district	Tomdi district	Uchkuduk district	Khatirchi district
Industry	26,9	7,7	1,7	99,0	100,0	23,2	42,2	98,5	47,8	86,2	100,0	100,0	49,6
Agriculture	94,8	96,0	88,9	100,0	85,3	95,1	87,7	99,1	99,1	94,5	99,6	99,7	94,6
Construction	74,7	79,1	78,2	86,1	100,0	99,4	93,8	76,9	100,0	49,6	19,1	93,1	100,0
Trade	83,8	93,8	84,3	93,4	94,5	99,3	97,0	98,8	92,5	98,6	99,2	99,6	97,8
Services	47,7	57,0	37,9	48,2	59,8	66,6	86,4	78,3	78,6	86,1	90,6	82,0	81,7
Export	29,0	9,0	2,1	98,4	100,0	32,9	100,0	97,9	7,4	4,4	99,8	99,4	16,5
Import	50,7	36,2	19,0	93,8	100,0	41,9	74,2	95,5	46,8	96,3	100,0	100,0	79,7

Based on the unique characteristics, conditions, and opportunities of regional development, and in accordance with the social and economic development programs of Navoi region, measures are being taken to further strengthen macroeconomic stability, increase the role and importance of the private sector in the economy, deepen structural reforms in key sectors, and enhance administrative reforms and the development of the social sector.

In the context of further economic development and liberalization, to study and analyze in more detail the positive results achieved in the SBPE sector of Navoi region’s economy, as well as the emerging negative trends, a comparative analysis of a number of socio-economic integrated indicators across regions was conducted (Table 2.8).

Table 4

Analysis of SBPE Development in the Cities and Districts of Navoi Region [5]

Year	Pareto-optimal set $\{M_1\}$	Moderately developed region set $\{M_2\}$	Low-performing region set $\{M_3\}$
2010 year	Karmana district	Navoi and Zarafshan cities, Kiziltepa, Khatirchi, Konimekh, Navbahor, Nurata, and Tomdi districts	Uchkuduk district
2023 year	Хатирчи, Қизилтепа ва Навбаҳор туманлари	Navoi and Zarafshan cities, Karmana, Konimekh, Nurata, and Tomdi districts	Uchkuduk district

For this, the results achieved by SBPE entities operating in the cities and districts of the region in 2010 and 2023 (the general ranking of descriptive factors) are classified based on the chosen criterion, specifically the share of those employed in SBPE relative to the total employed population in the economy. This classification can be done by arranging the data using the R_y and R_x rankings (based on the information in Table 2.9 and Figure 2.4).

Thus, in developing the prospects and strategies for the development of SBPE in the

region, the regions will be classified in the following sequence.

Figure 1. 2010 year

It is advisable to classify the cities and districts according to the development status of small business and private entrepreneurship into "priority ranks."

2010 year : $K_{kar} \succ K_{navo}, K_{zaf}, K_{qiz}, K_{xat}, K_{kon}, K_{navb}, K_{nur}, K_{tom} \succ K_{uchk}$.

2018 year: $K_{xat}, K_{qiz}, K_{navb} \succ K_{kar}, K_{navo}, K_{zaf}, K_{kon}, K_{nur}, K_{tom} \succ K_{uchk}$.

5-жадвал

Навойи вилояти шаҳар ва туманларида кичик бизнес ривожланишининг қиёсий таҳлили [6]

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Т/р	Вилоят шаҳар ва туманлари	КБНинг				Кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбиркорлик фаолиятини тавсифловчи кўрсаткичлар тизимчаси (хулуд аҳолиси сонига нисбатан)													
		Иқтисодийда банд бўлган аҳолига нисбатан улushi		2018 йил		КБХТда ташкил этилган иш	Саноат маҳсулоти ишлаб чиқариш	Халқ истеъмоли молларини ишлаб	Қишлоқ хўжалиги маҳсулотларини	Қурилиш ишлари	Чакана савдо	Пуллик хизмат	Юк айланиши	Йўловчи айланиши	Фермер	Дехқон	Хорижий инвестиция	Ранг суммаси	Умумий ранг
		2010 йил	Ранг	%	Ранг														
1.	Навойи шаҳри	53.1	7	26	7	2	1	1	9	1	1	7	3	9	9	1	45	1	
2.	Зарафшон шаҳри	49.9	9	25	9	2	3	10	2	2	2	4	1	9	9	8	59	3	
3.	Кармана тумани	58.5	2	72	2	5	3	3	3	3	4	5	2	4	8	4	46	2	
4.	Конимех тумани	54.7	5	70	5	8	5	5	8	5	3	2	8	6	7	3	68	5	
5.	Қизилтепа тумани	53.7	6	75	6	3	5	4	5	6	7	8	6	3	2	10	65	4	
6.	Навбахор тумани	58.2	3	80	3	6	10	1	6	10	6	9	4	1	6	6	74	6	
7.	Нурота тумани	57.9	4	74	4	4	7	6	4	7	10	6	7	5	4	9	76	7	
8.	Томди тумани	68.8	1	77	1	9	9	7	9	8	8	1	9	7	1	5	83	9	
9.	Учкудук тумани	45.9	10	22	10	10	4	8	9	4	5	3	5	8	8	7	79	8	
10.	Хатирчи тумани	50.3	8	80	8	1	6	4	2	7	9	10	10	2	3	2	65	4	

which do not host large industrial enterprises, were placed in the highest group. In contrast, Karmana and Konimekh districts, as well as Navoi city, were ranked in the lower groups due to their low indicators in this area.

When statistically grouping the cities and districts of the region by the share of SBPE in employment, Navbahor and Khatirchi districts were placed in the highest group. Meanwhile, Navoi and Zarafshan cities, as well as Uchkuduk district, were categorized in the lower group for this indicator.

In the context of further deepening economic reforms and the modernization of the economy, to study and analyze in more detail the positive results achieved in the SBPE sector of Navoi region's economy, as well as the emerging negative trends, a comparative analysis of a number of socio-economic integrated indicators across regions was conducted. As a result of the analysis, in 2010, the highest indicator was in Karmana district, while in 2022, improvements were observed in Khatirchi, Kiziltepa, and Navbahor districts, where the indicators were higher.

In 2010, Navoi city and Karmana district were the leaders in terms of the volume of investments made into the fixed capital of small business entities. Investment in small businesses was average in Kiziltepa, Navbahor, and Nurata districts, while it was the lowest in Uchkuduk and Tomdi districts. In 2022, Karmana district ranked first in terms of investment into the fixed capital of small businesses, followed by Navoi city, then Kiziltepa and Khatirchi districts, where average amounts of investment were attracted.

During the reporting period, the average investment return across all sectors of small entrepreneurship in the region increased by 2.1 times compared to the base period. This increase was primarily driven by a significant rise in investment return in Zarafshan city, Konimekh, and Nurata districts. As a result of the final index values, notable shifts in the indicators of Navoi city, Karmana, and Khatirchi districts can be highlighted.

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